

Health Implications of Covid-19 on Mathematics Students

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Abstract

The study titled health implications of COVID-19 on mathematics students reveals that COVID-19 pandemic has negative effects on the well being of mathematics students in the sense that it has affected the following areas such as health services for non-communicable diseases, service disruptions, reassignment of staff and postponing of screening, implementation of alternative strategies for continuing care, psychological, behavioral, interpersonal, children, **gender-based violence, health services, cash transfers and food assistance**, clinical guidance on pregnancy, intra-partum care and breastfeeding, contraception and family planning, violence against women and self-care interventions. In all, this paper recommends that governments should prioritize services preventing and responding to violence and deem them as essential services during emergency, there should be public health foundation for all network, world health organisation recommends that sexual and reproductive health, science-based responses, public health interventions should look at how to promote health equity and reduce inequality, there should be intensive testing and contact tracing, isolation of infected individuals, enforcement of isolation and wide use of face masks for the mitigation of COVID-19 pandemic and governments must ensure education response plans are gender and age responsive and reflect the lived realities of girls, children with disabilities and other marginalised children throughout the life cycle of education and schools should be supported to prevent and control the spread of COVID-19 with attention paid to protect students and staff from discrimination and stigma associated with the infection.

Keywords: COVID-19 symptoms, spread and risks, pandemic, health implications, Mathematics students and predictions.